

MATHEMATICS

EFFECT OF COVID-19 ON ACADEMIC RESULTS OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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Abstract

Teachers and students encountered various challenges to fulfill the academic requirement in COVID-19. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the effect of COVID-19 on students' academic performance at Mawlana Bhashani Science and Technology University. We enlist 468 university students in our research study. Chi-square testing, cross-tabulation, and frequency distribution were used to examine the data. The findings indicate that 87.4% of respondents took an online course, 90.4% took an online exam, 74.4% believe that online learning is less effective than in-person learning, and only 4.7% are extremely satisfied with their academic experiences during the pandemic. The results also designate that there is a significant correlation between academic performance and taking an online exam, as well as between academic performance and taking an online course. There is also a significant correlation between academic performance and the degree of satisfaction with academic activities.

Keywords: Academic results, COVID-19, Effect, University Students, MBSTU.

Introduction

The COVID-19 epidemic has caused the most significant disruption to education systems in human history, affecting approximately 1.6 billion students across more than 200 countries. Closures of schools, institutions, and other learning places have affected more than 94% of the world's student population (Pokhrel & Chhetri, 2021). To reduce COVID-19 transmission, numerous countries adopted infection preventive and control methods by limiting contact between people (*Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) – World Health Organization*, n.d.). Due to COVID-19, higher education institutions transitioned to online learning (Aguilera-Hermida, 2020). Online learning, sometimes known as remote learning, virtual learning, or distance learning, is a style of instruction in which students are not physically present in the classroom (Aguilera-Hermida, 2020). We can see that when covid-19 was identified in Bangladesh, the government issued a lockdown order. After March 17, 2020, Bangladesh's educational institutions have all been closed. To retain social distance, students from primary to tertiary levels are forced to sit at home rather than attend classes in educational institutions (Halim, 2021).

During covid-19, our institution continued academic activities online (such as lessons and tests), with the majority of our students attending online classes and taking exams. To continue with these online courses, both teachers and students face several difficulties.

Therefore, the purpose of the current study was to ascertain how COVID-19 affected the academic performance of MBSTU students. This study used a research methodology to examine the relationship between various factors (attending online classes, taking part in online exams, mental health concerns, etc.) and their effect on academic performance. It also presents the proportion of students who encountered problems with technology and communication, and how those problems affected their performance. The study's conclusion indicates that taking classes online has a detrimental effect on the students' academic performance.

Objectives of the study

- i. To investigate whether there is a relationship between COVID-19 and academic results.
- ii. To determine whether there is a correlation between online classes and academic outcomes.
- iii. To show the relationship between the degree of satisfaction of academic activities and the impact on academic results during COVID-19.

Materials and Methodology

The abrupt change to online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic is considered a social phenomenon (El Said, 2021a) that incorporates culture, technology, and human behavior, where different views must be considered (Abel Jr, 2020). Hence, the use of multiple research methods and the use of a multiplicity of techniques are essential (El Said, 2021b).

Data source

The MBSTU students are taken into consideration in this study, which is carried out utilizing the simple random sampling technique. We get data about 468 pupils. Students from each department, the residence halls, and other private housing closer to the university are chosen at random. Data was acquired in these study is both qualitative and quantitative by employing structured questionnaires. Background characteristics including sex, age, housing arrangement, personal income, marital status, and religion are included in the questionnaire. Additional factors include educational attainment, study duration, health problems encountered, technology problems, communication difficulties, participation in online exams, attendance in online classes, satisfaction with academic activities, and their recommendations are also included.

We have gathered a sample of data regarding students from various departments and years. We also gather data regarding their performance.

Method of Analysis

The relevant literature is evaluated from various published journals, official documents, books, reports, proceedings, etc. in order to meet the objectives. Both univariate and bivariate strategies have been used to achieve the study's goal. In order to investigate the relationship between the dependent and different independent variables, cross-tabulation analysis is conducted where univariate analysis is also presented in this stage.

Statistical Tool and Techniques

Univariate analysis

Univariate analysis is used to find the frequency distribution and to show different graphs of several variables in the study.

Bivariate Analysis

The frequency distribution is the initial stage for investigating the link between two variables. However, this frequency distribution does not provide quantification or testing of that relationship. For these reasons, it

is useful to investigate several indices that assess the extent of correlation, as well as statistical tests of the null hypothesis.

Chi-Square Test (χ^2)

A Chi-Square Test is used to explore the relationship between two categorical variables. Each of these variables can have two or more categories. It is often used in hypothesis testing, especially Pearson's Chi-square test.

Pearson's Chi-Square

$$\chi^2 = \sum_i \sum_j \frac{(O_{ij} - E_{ij})^2}{E_{ij}} \sim \chi^2(r - 1)(c - 1)$$

Where, (r-1)(c-1) degrees of freedom.

O_{ij} = Observed frequency.

E_{ij} = Expected frequency

P-value

The P-value is the minimum, exact level of significance. The P-value for a hypothesis test is the probability of obtaining a value of the test statistic as extreme as more than the one actually computed. The p-value for a statistic may be defined as the smallest value of which the null hypothesis can be rejected. If the p-value is greater than the level of significance, then we do not reject the null hypothesis.

Moreover, this analysis requires appropriate technological support because the study deals with a set of data. The analysis for this study was completed entirely on a personal computer using Microsoft Word and SPSS 20.

Results and Discussion

Cross tabulation for finding the association between participated online exam and impact on academic results.

Hypothesis-1:

H_0 : There is no association between participated online exam and academic result.

H_1 : There is an association between participated online exam and academic result.

Table-1

The relationship between taking an online exam and its effect on academic performance.

		Participated Online Exam		Total	Pearson Chi-Square	df	p-value
		Yes	No				
Impact on academic result	Positive	175	27	202	7.79	1	0.005
	Negative	243	15	258			
Total		418	42	460			

Figure-1: Respondent's involvement in an online test

Comment: Academic performance is significantly ($p < 0.05$) correlated with taking an online exam. Thus, the null hypothesis may be rejected. Participation in an online exam is associated to academic achievement.

Cross tabulation for finding the association between online learning and impact on academic results.

Hypothesis-2:

H_0 : There is no correlation between the effectiveness of online learning and academic results.

H_1 : There is a correlation between the effectiveness of online learning and academic results.

Table-2

The connection between the effectiveness of online learning and academic results.

		Online learning		Total	Pearson Chi-Square	df	p-value
		Yes	No				
Impact on academic result	Positive	71	130	201	21.07	1	0.00*
	Negative	43	215	258			
Total		114	345	459			

Figure-2: The effectiveness of online learning as perceived by the respondents.

Comment: This indicates that there is a significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation between the effectiveness of online learning and academic achievement. Thus, we can rule out the null hypothesis. Academic performance is correlated with online learning.

Cross tabulation for finding the association between mental health issue and impact on academic results..

Hypothesis-3:

H_0 : Academic performance and respondents' experiences with mental health issues are not related.

H_1 : Academic performance and respondents' experiences with mental health issues are related.

Table – 3

The connection between respondents' experiences with mental health issues and their effects on academic performance.

		Experienced any mental health issue		Total	Pearson Chi-Square	df	p-value
		Yes	No				
Impact on academic result	Positive	126	76	202	4.50	1	0.034
	Negative	185	73	258			
Total		311	149	460			

Figure- 3: Respondents' experiences with mental health issues

Comment: It is evident that there is a significant correlation ($p < 0.05$) between mental health issues. Thus, the null hypothesis may be rejected. Academic performance and respondents' experiences with mental health issues are related.

Cross tabulation for finding the association between compare online learning and impact on academic results.

Hypothesis-4:

H_0 : There is no correlation between the level of online learning comparison among respondents and its impact on academic results.

H_1 : There is a correlation between the level of online learning comparison among respondents and its impact on academic results.

Table-4

The association between the level of online learning comparison among respondents and impact on academic result.

		Compare online learning			Total	Pearson Chi-Square	df	p-value
		Better	Moderate/Similar	Less				
Impact on academic result	Positive	23	56	122	201	11.55	2	0.003
	Negative	19	44	194	257			
Total		42	100	316	458			

Figure- 4: The level of online learning comparison among respondents

Comment: The level of online learning comparison among respondents is highly associated ($p < 0.05$) with academic outcomes. So we may reject the null hypothesis. There is a link between comparison online learning and academic outcomes.

Cross tabulation for finding the association between academic activities and impact on academic results.

Hypothesis-5:

H_0 : There is no association between satisfied with academic activities and academic result.

H_1 : There is an association between the degree of satisfaction of academic activities and the impact on academic results.

Table-5

The association between the degree of satisfaction of academic activities and the impact on academic results.

		Satisfied with academic activities				Total	Pearson Chi-Square	df	p-value
		Strongly Satisfied	Satisfied	Moderate Satisfied	Not Satisfied				
Impact on academic result	Positive	10	44	75	68	197	9.93	3	0.0190
	Negative	12	36	85	123	256			
Total		22	80	160	191	453			

Figure-5: Respondent's degree of satisfaction with academic activities.

Comment: We observe a substantial ($p < 0.05$) correlation with academic activity satisfaction. Thus, the null hypothesis may be rejected. Academic achievements and satisfaction with academic activity are related.

Conclusion

Finding out does COVID-19 affected MBSTU students' academic performance was the aim of this study. Following the pandemic, we conducted study on a number of issues, some of which have been correlated to academic performance. According to the study's findings, there is a significant association between online courses and exams and academic results. Based on this correlation, it is possible to assume that COVID-19 had an effect on academic results. Therefore, this study represents a significant advancement in the identification of variables that affect academic results during pandemic.

Recommendation

- To mitigate the pandemic's impact, universities should implement short-term semesters.
- The authorities should offer mental health and counseling services to students.
- The institution should use online learning in addition to traditional classroom instruction, as they did during the pandemic.
- In order to increase students' level of satisfaction, authorities should concentrate on academic activities.

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